

A-Cube Way for Research Learning Experience: View of Students

B. Naduni Hansika Abeywardena¹, Chatura Lavanga Mendis¹, Duangthida Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya¹, Ei Ei Lwin¹, Yasiru Shikshitha Benaragama¹, Shih-Hsuan Wei^{1,2}, Chih-Fan Tan^{1,2}

¹ A-Cube Research Group, Department of Industrial Systems Engineering, Asian Institute of Technology, Pathumthani, Thailand

² Department of Industrial Engineering and Enterprise Information, Tunghai University, Taichung, Taiwan

Email: nhabey93@gmail.com, lavanga.mendis@gmail.com, duangthidaHNA@gmail.com, eieilwin26@gmail.com, fluxes94@gmail.com, michellewei30@gmail.com, victoria841211@gmail.com

Abstract

Conducting research and presenting the findings are typically compulsory for engineering graduate students to fulfill the requirements for graduation. It is a means of preparing the students for a successful career before they leave the schools. It is no longer about transferring knowledge, but instead about building their competence. Once the students enter the industrial environment and face different kinds of problems, they should be confident enough to analyze the situation and find the solution by themselves. Presented in this paper is the view on their learning experiences of students in the A-Cube research environment in the Industrial Engineering Program at Asian Institute of Technology, Thailand, where the students are required to achieve creative solutions for challenging tasks on a strict schedule constructively and collaboratively. The students' perspective on their reported research learning experience journeys were classified into four different personas – considering different levels of education and areas of research – and described based on the LOVE learning experience model developed by the group. The results unfold a set of similar and different research learning activities and experiences between the four personas designing to support the students' research competent development in the group.

Keywords: Research Learning Experience; Engineering Education; Building Competence; A-Cube, LOVE.

1 Introduction

Different teaching approaches are used around the world to achieve one simple goal; to prepare the students to have a successful career once they leave the learning environment. According to the world economic forum, it's a requirement for employees of 2020, to have the following skills namely, complex problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, people management, coordinating with others, emotional intelligence, judgement and decision making, service orientation, negotiation and cognitive flexibility (Gray, 2016). In higher education, especially in the master's degree program, besides taking coursework, conducting research is mandatory. Conducting research will transform a person from being a consumer of knowledge to a producer of knowledge (Lovitts, 2005; Gardener, 2008). Scientists and faculty members have revealed that their research experiences were vital for the success in their respective fields. It is, therefore, of interest to investigate on their research learning journeys that transform them to be the producers of knowledge.

A-Cube Research Group – formed more than a decade ago in the Department of Industrial Systems Engineering, Asian Institute of Technology – has produced more than seventy graduates to support academic institutions and industry. Five of them are now faculty members in engineering. A few are operating their own business. Most of the research works produced by the group have been presented in international conferences and published in international journals (Koomsap, 2017). At A-Cube, students work in various areas of research, from Adaptive Layered Manufacturing to Customer Oriented Manufacturing. The team leader guides the students through a set of phases involving activities that help to stimulate their thinking while improving their skills and helping them discover their true potential.

This paper discusses the student's perspective of the effectiveness of active learning, the techniques involved in providing the students with a great research learning experience at A-Cube. The students' perspective on their reported journeys were classified into four different personas – considering different levels of education and areas of research – and described based on the LOVE learning experience model (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap, 2017) developed by the group.

The next section gives a brief understanding of the LOVE model and the types of learning experiences, followed by the third section which explains about the A-Cube research group. The fourth section describes the methodology followed and the results obtained. The paper is concluded by discussing the phases in the life of a student of A-Cube and their experiences throughout their journey at A-Cube. Future work is provided in the last section.

2 LOVE Model

Varieties of teaching approaches are applied and offered in different universities and thus students perceive different learning experiences throughout their academic journey. In some teaching approaches such as visual and virtual laboratory activities, students will have to actively involve and are immersed in them to understand the subject. However, in lectures and seminars, they just pay attention and absorb the knowledge and information provided by the lecturer or speaker. Students will have to interact with different teaching approaches offered until they successfully complete their learning journey. Therefore, the LOVE model (Figure 1) has been developed with the aim of assessing the students learning experience. It has been applied in assessing master's student research experience and its application suggests the supervisors adjust and improve their supervisory styles for the students to possess better research experiences (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap, 2018).

Figure 1. LOVE model (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap, 2017)

In the LOVE model, student learning experiences are classified into four types as learner (L), observer (O), visitor (V) and experimenter (E) regarding two dimensions: student involvement (passive and active involvement), and the nature of learning (absorption and immersion). The students will have the richest learning experience when they meet the four types of learning experiences in their learning journey. The definitions of the four types of learning experiences are explained as follows.

Learner: When a student actively participates in the learning activities and absorbs knowledge and information given by the lecturer or instructor, he/she is experiencing as a learner. Examples are class discussion and individual presentation.

Observer: When a student passively participates in the learning activities and absorbs the knowledge and information delivered by the lecturer or instructor, he/she is experiencing as an observer. Examples are lecture and seminar.

Visitor: When a student passively participates and immerses in the learning activities to gain knowledge and information, he/she is experiencing as a visitor. Examples are field trip and conference.

Experimenter: When a student actively participates and immerses in the learning activities to take action to gain knowledge and information, he/she is experiencing as an experimenter. An example is experimenting in a laboratory.

3 A-Cube Research Group

Formed over a decade ago, the research focus of A-Cube, founded by the team leader Dr. Pisut Koomsap, has evolved from its initial three "A"s namely, Adaptive Layered Manufacturing, Abrasive Waterjet Technology, and Automotive Technology, towards more trending areas like Customer Oriented Manufacturing including design for customer experience, co-created product design, image-based additive manufacturing from 3D computer-aided design (CAD) models, reverse engineering and sketch-based modeling, and flexible automation for rapid personalized production. "Make it simple" being no longer viable with the rapid development in engineering fields, future engineers will have to provide creative solutions, be resourceful and have critical thinking in order to succeed, thereby introducing the current motto "Thinking Beyond Engineering".

At A-cube, the team leader stimulates the members thinking while improving their skills and helping them discover their true potential. Working to a strict schedule, collaboration, constructive criticism, challenging tasks, and creative solutions are key features of our group. Progress presentation sessions held every two weeks helps improve the presentation skills of all group members, while making them think on their feet. Different areas of research are discussed in these meeting sessions, giving the students a broader view of the challenges ahead. The room allocated for the A-Cube research group is arranged in such a way that students from the same area of research are grouped together in a cluster. This enables the students to develop their research idea based on constructive criticism of other group members. Continuous interaction with different people from different nationalities helps improve communication skills as well as the ability to work in multicultural environments.

4 A-Cube Research Learning Experience

4.1 Methodology

During the postgraduate program, some students who completed their research at A-Cube within the last five years were requested to submit an individual report describing their research experience. The report consisted of the students' individual experiences, from the day that they joined the research group until the day they completed their postgraduate degree, and the types of their gained research experience classified by the LOVE model. Before forming the report, articles on the LOVE model, and some concise explanations were provided to them to aid their understanding. The students spent about a week to form their concise report.

Submitted reports were reviewed. The first round of review aimed to separate between different personas concerning their level of education (master student, doctoral student) and areas of research. The master students who submitted the reports spent one year on their journey. A few of them spent one or two more semesters to complete the research journey. The following are the four personas according to the reported research experiences.

Persona 1: The doctoral student who has completed the master's degree in A-Cube and then re-joined for the doctoral program. The student has spent a minimum of four years (one year as a Master student and three years as a doctoral student) at A-Cube. Considering the last five years, one student falls into this category.

Persona 2: The master student who works on the theoretical aspect of engineering, namely customer experience and service failure prevention. Considering the last five years, ten students fall into this category.

Persona 3: The master student who works on manufacturing – designing and developing prototypes to verify their concepts related to machining. Some key areas of interest of this persona are current research trends like

smart manufacturing and additive manufacturing. Considering the last five years, twelve students fall into this category.

Persona 4: The master student who works on simulation. The student was in the dual master's degree program and was involved in simulation-based projects like developing intelligent warehouses for customized production and developing flexible assembly management systems for customized products. Considering the last five years, two students fall into this category.

Next, the second round of review was conducted. Following the guideline given by Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap in 2018, the journeys described in the reports of each persona were carefully looked into details to itemize their research activities and assess their research experience. Collected activities could be separated into five phases in accordance with the LOVE learning experience model. During this process, some students were contacted or interviewed to retrieve additional information on their reported journeys – for example, when their reported types of experience were unclear.

4.2 Results and Discussion

Figure 2 represents the five phases of the research learning activities of the four personas as mentioned in relation to the LOVE model. The journey of all students at A-Cube starts with the proposal phase which is after the completion of coursework. Before working on their own research, the students are required to attend weekly group meetings at which the seniors will update the progress of their individual research areas. They will observe all the presented research work and select an area of interest by exchanging ideas with the seniors and discussing it with the advisor. "When I started the research, initially I discussed my interested research area with the supervisor. During the discussion, I had to actively generate ideas such as the interesting points of my research area and what I would like to do next and also gained helpful insights from the supervisor" was one view expressed by a student from persona four. Through discussions and the exchanging of ideas, they will move from the "Observer" experience towards the "Learner" experience. The "Experimenter" experience begins once they accomplish the literature review and identify the thesis objective. In the proposal phase of figure 2, it can be seen that persona 4 lacks the third activity; exchanging ideas with the seniors about their research since they are involved in a dual degree program thereby reducing the opportunity to interact with seniors. The experience type of each persona remains constant throughout the activities of this phase.

During the research phase, the group leader will stimulate the students thinking by sharing research papers in their respective fields of interest. Each persona makes the effort to explore their selected area of interest and present their findings at the group gatherings. At these gatherings, all personas will be visitors to each other's fields of interest in the sense that they will eventually try to grab some knowledge about each other's areas of interest, and passively immerse into the situation. But in the case of a persona attending a seminar of another research group, they will passively absorb the knowledge, but they will not have the capacity to be immersed in the situation entirely, thereby making them an observer. An example of this would be persona two whose area of interest is about customer experience attending a seminar related to nanotechnology. One such student had mentioned in their report that "When I listened to the progress presentations made by my colleagues since it was explained section-wise every week, I gradually got to know about their areas of interest. When attending seminars, even though I tried to grab as much information as possible during the seminar which usually lasted for two hours, I was unable to do so". Another scenario of the observer experience was seen in the situation where persona four was attending online lectures (activity 15) since they were involved in a dual degree program. The activities where all personas act as experimenters in this phase will differ according to their fields of interest.

Phase	Activity	Persona 1				Persona 2				Persona 3				Persona 4			
		L	O	V	E	L	O	V	E	L	O	V	E	L	O	V	E
Proposal	1 Observing seniors' research		●				●				●				●		
	2 Observing the feedback given by the advisor to the seniors			●				●				●				●	
	3 Exchanging ideas with the seniors about their research	●				●				●							
	4 Identifying area of interest	●				●				●				●			
	5 Discussing the area of interest with the advisor	●				●				●				●			
	6 Accomplishing literature review			●				●				●				●	
	7 Identifying thesis title			●				●				●				●	
	8 Identifying thesis objective			●				●				●				●	
Research	9 Updating research progress			●				●				●				●	
	10 Discussing research with colleagues and others			●				●				●				●	
	11 Listening to colleagues presentations and gathering information		●				●				●						
	12 Sharing knowledge among advisor and students via research papers	●				●				●				●			
	13 Visiting laboratories and research centers		●				●				●				●		
	14 Attending seminars of other research groups		●				●				●				●		
	15 Participating in online lectures																
	16 Preparing for research presentation			●				●				●				●	
	17 Identifying research concept			●				●				●				●	
	18 Doing a case study			●				●				●				●	
	19 Simulating and testing on technical aspects related to area of interest																
	20 Developing the prototype																
	21 Testing the precision and accuracy of the prototype																
	22 Identifying execution plan			●				●				●				●	
	23 Analyzing research result			●				●				●				●	
	24 Drawing research conclusion and recommendation			●				●				●				●	
	25 Rehearsal			●				●				●				●	
	26 Dissertation defense			●				●				●				●	
Publication	27 Preparing manuscripts for publications			●				●				●				●	
	28 Publishing the dissertation as journals			●				●				●				●	
	29 Attending international conferences		●				●				●				●		
	30 Presenting research papers in international conference			●				●				●				●	
	31 Participating in a PhD students session in a conference	●															
	32 Participating in workshops	●															
	33 Social networking in conferences		●				●				●				●		
	34 Collaborating with other researchers			●				●				●				●	
Assistant	35 Assisting in organizing a student conference							●				●					
	36 Developing a smart factory											●					
	37 Attending technical workshops									●							
Doctoral Training	38 Participating in an Erasmus Plus project on curriculum development			●													
	39 Taking meeting minutes reports			●													
	40 Co-developing teaching and learning materials for a newly developed course			●													
	41 Assisting an instructor in classes			●													
	42 Assisting in organizing a student conference			●													
	43 Assisting in organizing an international conference			●													
	44 Reviewing abstracts as a reviewer for an international conference			●													
		6	5	3	23	4	5	4	15	5	5	2	19	3	5	2	15

Figure 2. Classification of activities with respect to phases and the journey of personas

Activities like preparing manuscripts (activity 27), presenting research papers (activity 30), and collaborating with other researchers (activity 34) in the publication phase require the students to actively immerse to gain knowledge and information, thereby giving them the experience of an Experimenter. As students, the four personas had the opportunity of observing the activity of social networking between the team leader and other personnel who were participating in the conference. Differing from the other three personas, persona one being a doctoral student, has had the opportunity of participating in PhD student sessions and workshops where she had played the role of a learner.

The assistant phase is undergone mainly by persona three. While being involved in a project for smart manufacturing, one student had mentioned in their report that "By being involved in this smart factory project, I had to investigate countless methods of approaching the problem of building an efficient AGV fleet management system before finally settling down on the implemented system, which I found out to be the best possible way to approach to the problem". This statement clearly shows the active immersive experience of the student in their assistant phase. Another major point to note in this phase is that the same activity can have different experiences for different personas. For example, for persona three, the activity of assisting in organizing a student conference is an experimenter experience because they were actively involved in the organizing of the event whereas persona 2 has had the experience of a visitor since they had attended the event but haven't been involved actively in organizing the event. After the research phase, persona one had directly transferred to the doctoral program and had to actively participate in organizing the event as part of her doctoral training. This is one example where it's clear that the activities are independent of the phases. Even though the type of experience is the same (experimenter) for both persona one and persona three in the case of organizing the student conference, the level of effort put and understanding are different.

The doctoral training phase is present only for persona one. In this phase, all the activities that she had gone through fall under the category of experimenter hence suggesting that in comparison to other phases, the doctoral training phase had transformed the students to be more independent.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

From the results, it is clearly seen that students at A-Cube gain all types of the LOVE experience during their research journey regardless of their field of research interest. They undergo many phases throughout their journey in which through different activities, they gain different experiences. These experiences are varied according to the personas, their field of research, the research activities, and how they engage in these activities. At the beginning, the activities are more focused on Learning and Observing; whereas, in the latter phases, they are shifted towards Visitor and Experimenter. Each phase holds a set of common and unique activities that molds the students to become their own unique confident personalities – how a student evolves from a dependent state more towards a confident, independent individual with a unique personality.

However, there is still room for improvement. To enrich A-Cube research experience, more research activities should be designed to provide stronger experience on the dimension of visiting experience. Technology-supported teaching methods such as virtual lab tour may be brought in to explode the students into other fields of research and expand their vision. Collaboration between other research groups can also be considered to create the stronger research learning environment and enhance their research competence.

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